

Modelling the phase behaviour of fluid systems relevant for carbon-capture processes: the importance of SO_x and NO_x

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The fluid phase equilibria of carbon dioxide in aqueous carbon-capture solvents, such as monoethanolamine and other more-sophisticated solvents, have been studied in depth over recent years. However, real flue-gas streams contain impurities, such as SO_x and NO_x; these can adversely affect carbon-capture plant as well as influencing the phase equilibria. The development of a modelling capability to assess the impact of these impurities on the thermodynamics of these fluid systems is a necessary precursor to the design and operation of successful carbon-capture infrastructure. Here, using the state-of-the-art group-contribution SAFT- γ Mie equation of state, working within the framework of HiRECORD, a “world’s-first” project to demonstrate a 10t/d CO₂ capture plant using Rotating-Packed-Bed absorber and desorber with a bespoke designer solvent, we embark on the first step of this task via the development of models for sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen (II) oxide and nitrogen (IV) oxide, three of the more-important SO_x and NO_x in this context. The nature of each of these fluids presents challenges to modelling. For example, the behaviour of SO₂ is strongly influenced by the large dipole and quadrupole moments. Moreover, each of NO and NO₂ are free radicals; the octet rule is not fulfilled for the nitrogen in either of these molecules, providing a driving force for dimerization and resulting in both nitrogen (II) oxide and nitrogen (IV) oxide comprising mixtures of two NO_x: NO + N₂O₂, and NO₂ + N₂O₄ (respectively); this chemistry introduces interesting subtleties in the model development. We examine the impact of these SO_x and NO_x impurities on the phase equilibria of mixtures relevant for carbon capture. The facility of SAFT- γ Mie to incorporate intermolecular association renders it an ideal tool to address these challenges.

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